

A highly active catalyst supported molecular sieves-NaHCO₃ mixture for the selective and advantageous *N*-monoalkylation of amines

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Abstract : Amines are mono-*N*-alkylated by alkylmesylates in the presence of catalyst supported molecular sieves-NaHCO₃ mixture in a regioselective, chemoselective and non-toxic process. Observed chemoselectivity is supported by 'DFT'.

Keywords : Amines, alkylmesylates, regioselective, chemoselective, DFT.

Introduction

Selective *N*-monoalkylation of amines is of fundamental importance in organic synthesis¹⁻⁶ and allylic secondary amines are useful building blocks in organic chemistry⁷, making search for improved procedures for their synthesis an attractive research field. As revealed from literature, monoalkylation of aniline is highly important in industry⁶. Various methods of *N*-alkylation (either using aliphatic amine or aromatic amine) have been developed⁸ from time to time of which the most common method of *N*-alkylation is the reaction of an alkyl halide and an amine in the presence of base⁹. However, this methodology is of limited use because of environmental hazards⁹. There are a large number of reports on the alkylation of aniline (aromatic amine) by reaction with alcohols in the presence of solid acid catalysts¹⁰, transitional metal-based catalysts^{9,10,12,13}. All these methods have serious limitations producing in addition to monoalkylated product, di- or tri-alkylated products^{1-6,9,13} and in most cases dialkylated products were obtained as the major products^{11,12}. Recently, selective synthesis of monoalkylated aryl amines were achieved by amination of aniline with different alkyl amines via alkyl transfer process¹⁴ involving Shvo catalyst. Hwu *et al.* also demonstrated the method of *N*-monoalkylation process during the synthesis of Tamsulosin by coupling aliphatic amine with

alkyl mesylate but no systematic study is done till date to establish the efficiency of that process¹⁵. In classical methodologies, the synthesis of secondary amines is generally complicated by the formation of significant amounts of *N*-dialkylation products, which lowers the chemoselectivity and the economy of the process. The use of inorganic catalysts such as zeolites¹⁶ has been reported to provide selectively *N*-allylaniline derivatives. Nevertheless, an excess of amine (to prevent over allylation) and extended reaction times are demanded. Moreover, zeolite-catalysed mono *N*-alkylation of arylenediamines has been reported very recently¹³. Alkaline aluminosilicates have shown their efficacy for alkylating both aliphatic and aromatic amines. The capability of aluminosilicate ion to catalyse *N*-alkylation has been related, as shown in Fig. 1, to its ability to form a hydrogen bond with the amine proton, thereby enhancing the Lewis acid behaviour of the metal⁷. Herein, an efficient improved method of selective *N*-alkylation of amines (both aliphatic and aromatic) using molecular sieves-NaHCO₃-celite in ethanol at reflux is described. The synthetic process is represented in Scheme 1 Although a small excess of mesylate (electrophilic reagent) was used, the corresponding *N*-monoalkylated product was always recovered as the major product with good isolated yields (85-90%) along with some dialkylated products (5-10%). Unreacted amines were recovered successfully.

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Fig. 1. Mechanism of molecular sieves- NaHCO_3 -celite catalysed *N*-alkylation.

Scheme 1

Table 1. *N*-Alkylation of amines using different alkyl or allyl mesylate

Entry	Substrate	Alkylating agent (R ² -OMs) R ²	Time (h)	Product	Yield (%) ^a	Ref.
1	$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{NH}_2$	Butyl	2	$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_3$	82	1f
2		Butyl	2		86	1b
3		Decyl	2		87	1c
4		Butyl	2		85	1d
5		Methyl	2		88	13
6		Butyl	2		86	13
7		Octyl	2		87	2b
8		Decyl	2		88	2c
9		Methyl	2		89	3b
10		Butyl	2		90	3c

11		88	3d			
12		87	3e			
13		89	4b			
14		90	4c			
15		85	7c			
16		87	7b			
17		88	7d			
18		86	7e			
19		90	7f			
20		90	7f			
21		90	-			

^aYields refer to those of purified products characterized by IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopic data.

^bProduct characterized through spectroscopic and analytical data.

In fact, experimental results indicated that *N,N*-dialkyl amine production decreased as the molecular size of the electrophilic reagent decreased. Interestingly, *o*-phenylenediamines (entry 18–20, Table 1) gave regioselective allylation product and the regioselectivity was further established with the formation of benzodiazocine derivative (entry 21, Table 1). However, as indicated by the results in Table 1, the electronic environment of the different aromatic amines did not affect the reaction yields to a large extent.

To study the influence of the solvent, the results obtained using different polar solvents such as, ethanol, ethyl acetate and acetonitrile. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Solvent effect on molecular sieves-NaHCO₃-celite catalyzed alkylation of amine with butyl mesylate

Amine	Alkylating agent	Solvent	<i>N</i> -Mono-alkylated amine (%)	<i>N,N</i> -Dialkylated amine (%)
	ButylOMs	EtOH	90	6
	ButylOMs	EtOAc	90	6
	ButylOMs	CH ₃ CN	90	6

Clearly, the solvent did not alter the product formation, but the reaction was more sluggish in these solvents if carried out at room temperature. The reaction provided

optimum yield after 72 h at room temperature. Moreover, changing the electrophilic reagent from mesylate to tosylate¹⁷ (the reactions of *p*-anisidine with butyl mesylate and with butyl tosylate were compared) did not change the reaction course at all.

The molecular sieves-NaHCO₃-celite combination¹⁸ have shown their efficacy instead of NaHCO₃ alone or molecular sieves alone on the celite surface for alkylating both aliphatic and aromatic amines (Table 3).

Table 3. Catalyst effect on catalysed alkylation of amine

Amine	Alkylating agent	Catalyst	<i>N</i> -Alkylated product (%)	<i>N,N</i> -Dialkylated product (%)
	ButylOMs	NaHCO ₃ / celite	69	12
	ButylOMs	Molecular sieves/ celite	75	15
	ButylOMs	Molecular sieves/ NaHCO ₃ /celite	90	10

Presumably, NaHCO₃-celite under the condition of the experiment absorbs liberated CH₃SO₃[⊖] and protonated aluminosilicate more tightly thereby shifting the equilibrium to the product(s) side. Interestingly, an efficient regioselectivity was observed during the alkylation of *o*-phenylenediamine (entry 18–21, Table 1) which confirm the result obtained in mono-*N*-alkylation of arylenediamines¹⁹. In addition, chemoselectivity⁵ was observed during alkylation or allylation between aliphatic and aromatic amine (Table 4), which is in accordance with the quantum chemical calculations at Density Functional Theory (DFT) level using Gaussian 03W²⁰ software.

Quantum chemical calculation :

Quantum chemical calculations at Density Functional Theory (DFT) level using Gaussian 03W²⁰ software have

been performed to get theoretical understanding of the studied reaction and to complement the experimental findings. During the course of reaction, the nucleophilic center, i.e. the nitrogen atom(s) attacks the alkyl center to form secondary amino derivatives. Hence, the amount of negative charge and/or the electron occupancy may predict the possible path of the nitrogen. To get a general idea we have performed structural calculations at DFT level using B3LYP functional and 6-31G** basis set for several single and double amino substituted benzene derivatives in the ground state. We have also calculated Mulliken atomic charge density and Natural Bond Orbital (NBO) analysis for all the optimized geometry of each compound. Mulliken charge is based on the Mulliken population analysis which estimates partial atomic charge. Natural Bond Orbital Analysis^{21,22} has an appealing aspect of highlighting the individual bonds and lone-pairs that play a vital role in the chemical processes. The NBO analysis transfers the delocalized MOs into the localized ones. The interaction between field (e.g. the lone-pair) and antibonding orbitals represents the deviation of the molecule from the Lewis structure and can be used as a measure of delocalization due to intramolecular hydrogen bonds. It can provide the electronic occupancy of individual bond, lone pair orbital and their hybridization scheme.

Structurally the flexibility of aliphatic amine substituted compounds can give rise to several conformers with respect to the spatial orientation of the group about the freely rotating single bonds and di-substituted amino derivatives may have the probability of hydrogen bonding between an amino nitrogen with hydrogen of another amino nitrogen atom. For the main focusing molecule 5 (Table 5), it is found that the flexibility at the aliphatic amine side tries to form several conformers with respect to its spatial orientation (Fig. 1). However, with all possible initial geometry it is found that the molecule exists at the global minimum structure where there is a hydrogen bond between amino hydrogen of aromatic amine with the lone-pair of nitrogen of aliphatic amino group. This indicates

Table 4. Chemoselective alkylation of aliphatic amine over aromatic one

Entry	Substrate (S)	Electrophilic reagent (ER)	S : ER	Time (h)	Product	Yield (%)	Ref.
22		82	1e				
23		81	7g				

Table 5. Some parameters obtained from the optimized geometry at DFT level (B3LYP/6-31g)

Molecule	Mullikan atomic charge at N-atom	Natural charge at N-atom	Electron occupancy at N-atom	Hybridization of lone-pair electron at the N-centre
Phenylamine (1)	-0.817733 ^a	-0.84560	1.82045	s (0.00%) p 1.00 (100.00%)
Benzylamine (2)	-0.701816	-0.92117	1.95098	s (10.40%) p 8.62 (89.60%)
Benzene-1,2-diamine (3)	-0.793016 ^a	-0.87413	1.85756	s (6.09%) p 15.43 (93.91%)
2-Aminomethylbenzylamine (4)	-0.697579	-0.92300	1.93967	s (13.69%) p 6.30 (86.31%)
2-Aminomethylphenylamine (5)	-0.682878	-0.91357	1.94552	s (14.07%) p 6.11 (85.93%)
	-0.803563 ^a	-0.85447	1.79643	s (2.48%) p 39.33 (97.52%)
	-0.715252	-0.93328	1.93679	s (13.57%) p 6.37 (86.43%)

^aAromatic N-atom.

Fig. 2. Structure of 2-aminomethyl-phenylamine.

that the lone-pair of nitrogen of aliphatic amino group is less available for further reaction or hydrogen bond has to break for the availability of lone-pair for further reaction. Relevant calculated parameters for the optimized structure are shown in Table 5.

During the course of the reaction, the lone-pair of nitrogen attacks to R²-group (electrophilic reagent) to form the desired product. Therefore, it is obvious that the negative charge density at the nitrogen site may control the direction of the reaction and the selectivity of product formation. As shown in the Table 5, the Mulliken population analysis of the optimized structures for all compounds revealed that the negative charge at the aromatic nitrogen is more than the aliphatic nitrogen and the *p*-character of the lone-pair electron is more for the aromatic nitrogen than the aliphatic nitrogen. This is obvious, because aromatic amino group containing nitrogen atom's lone-pair is involved in resonance stabilization with the benzene π -electron. In some compounds the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding may be responsible for less negative charge at the aliphatic nitrogen center as aliphatic nitrogen lone-pair forms hydrogen bond with

hydrogen of other amino nitrogen atom. Particularly, the molecule 5 (Table 5) has different types of nitrogen center – one is the aliphatic nitrogen and another is the aromatic nitrogen. From the Mulliken scheme it is expected that the formation of secondary amine derivative favours at the aromatic nitrogen as it has more negative charge than aliphatic nitrogen. However, experimentally it is found that aliphatic nitrogen prefers the reaction over aromatic nitrogen. Therefore, Mulliken atomic charge may not explain the reaction pathways. On the other hand, NBO analysis provides a more vivid picture of electron occupancy and natural charge as it describes localized MOs. As seen in Table 5, the natural charge at the nitrogen center(s) and electron occupancy at the nitrogen lone-pair orbitals obtained from NBO analysis of the optimized geometry of all compounds show that aliphatic nitrogen atoms have more calculated natural negative charge than the aromatic nitrogen atoms. Similarly, the electron occupancy at the aliphatic nitrogen lone-pair orbitals is more than the aromatic nitrogen lone-pair orbitals. Thus NBO calculation fully supports the fact that during the course of substitution reaction to form the secondary amine product first substitution favours at the aliphatic nitrogen than the aromatic nitrogen atom and these results fully complement the experimental findings.

In conclusion, the present procedure of selective *N*-monoalkylation (including regioselectivity) and chemoselective amine monoalkylation provides a very simple and efficient methodology for making 'C-N' bond. Chemoselectivity achieved in this protocol was also observed in methods reported earlier⁵, but this method employs simple, inexpensive and non-toxic reagent combination making this procedure advantageous for applications in organic synthesis.

Experimental

Column chromatography purifications were conducted on silica gel (230–400 mesh). Thin layer chromatography was carried out on aluminium sheets precoated with silica gel 60F₂₅₄ (Macherey-Nagel, Merk). The spots were visualized under UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm) and/or I₂ was used as revealing system. IR spectra were recorded as KBr discs with a Perkin-Elmer Fourier Transform spectrometer. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in 500 MHz Bruker and 300 MHz Bruker Supercon NMR respectively, and mass spectra were recorded in LC-MS-MS of Water Micro Mass instruments.

General procedure for the synthesis of mesylate :

A suspension of alcohol (4 mmol) in methylene chloride (10 mL) was treated with triethylamine (8 mmol) at 25°C, and the resulting mixture was cooled to 0–5 °C and then methanesulphonyl chloride (4 mmol) was added dropwise at that temperature. The resulting reaction mixture was subsequently stirred at room temperature for 2 h. After the completion of the reaction the reaction mixture was transferred to a separatory funnel with the aid of more DCM. The mixture was first extracted with ice water, followed by 10% HCl acid, saturated NaHCO₃, saturated brine. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to get a light yellow oily product (quantitative yield), which was pure enough for further uses.

General procedure for the synthesis of secondary amines :

Amine (1 mmol) and mesylate²³ (1.1 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of sodium bicarbonate (5 mmol) and celite (1 g) in ethanol (15 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen. After checking the TLC the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then the solid was removed through filtration (via sintered glass funnel). The solid was then washed with ethanol (3 × 5 mL). Removal of solvent (*in vacuo*) followed by column chromatography over silica gel (230–400 mesh) furnished the pure desired amine as an oily compound.

Physical and spectral data of all the synthesized compounds are summarized as below :

1 : Butyloctylamine : yield 82% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3136 (N–H), 2929 (–CH₂–), 1399 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 5.5 and 6.5 Hz, octyl), 0.93 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 and 7 Hz, butyl), 1.29 (16H, bs, butyl and octyl), 2.6 (4H, bs, butyl and octyl); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ_c 13.92, 20.45, 22.79, 23.77, 27.21, 29.26, 31.74, 38.76, 52.84; MS : *m/z* 186.2 (M⁺).

2 : Benzylbutylamine : yield 86% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3135 (N–H), 2926 (–CH₂–), 1397 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.90 (3H, q, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, butyl), 1.35 (2H, q, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, butyl), 1.49 (2H, q, *J* 7.5 Hz, butyl), 2.63 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, butyl), 3.79 (2H, s, benzyl), 7.24 (1H, t, *J* 4.5 Hz, Ar–H), 7.32 (4H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz, Ar–H); MS : *m/z* 163.9 (M⁺).

3 : Benzyldecylamine : yield 87% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3136 (N–H), 2925 (–CH₂–), 1398 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 7 and 6.5 Hz, decyl), 1.26 (14H, bs, decyl), 1.48–1.55 (2H, m, decyl), 2.62 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, decyl), 3.79 (2H, s, benzyl), 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz, Ar–H), 7.32 (4H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz, Ar–H); MS : *m/z* 248.1 (M⁺).

4 : Butylphenethylamine : yield 85% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3400 (N–H), 2925 (–CH₂–), 1456 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.99 (3H, q, *J* 7.5 and 7 Hz, butyl), 1.26–1.22 (2H, m, butyl), 1.42–1.48 (2H, m, butyl), 2.62 (2H, t, *J* 10 and 5 Hz, phenethyl), 2.81 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 6.5 Hz, phenethyl), 2.88 (2H, t, *J* 6.5 and 7 Hz, butyl), 7.20 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, Ar–H), 7.29 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 8 Hz, Ar–H); MS : *m/z* 178.0 (M⁺).

5 : Methylphenylamine : yield 88% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3398 (N–H), 2925 (–CH₃), 1514 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.77 (3H, s, methyl), 6.58 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar–H), 6.66 (1H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, Ar–H), 7.11–7.14 (2H, m, Ar–H); MS : *m/z* 108.1 (M⁺).

6 : Butylphenylamine : yield 86% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3429 (N–H), 2923 (–CH₂–), 1633 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.96 (3H, t, *J* 7.3 and 7.35 Hz, butyl), 1.43 (2H, q, *J* 7.2, 7.5 and 7.45 Hz, butyl), 1.60 (2H, q, *J* 7.4, 7.3 and 7.35 Hz, butyl), 3.11 (2H, t, *J* 7.1 and 7 Hz, butyl), 6.6 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar–H), 6.68 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 and 7.25 Hz, Ar–H), 7.17 (2H, t, *J* 7.75 and 7.55 Hz, Ar–H); MS : *m/z* 150.2 (M⁺).

7 : Octylphenylamine : yield 87% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3411 (N–H), 2925 (–CH₂–), 1603 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.91 (3H, t, *J* 6 and 7 Hz, octyl), 1.32 (8H, t, *J* 6.5 and 5 Hz, octyl), 1.42 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, octyl), 1.61–1.67 (2H, m, octyl), 3.13 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, octyl), 3.61 (1H, bs, NH), 6.63 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar–H), 6.71 (1H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, Ar–H), 7.20 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, Ar–H); MS : *m/z* 206.4 (M⁺).

8 : Decylphenylamine : yield 88% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3463 (N–H), 3020 (–CH₂–), 1216 (C–C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 5.5 and 7 Hz, decyl), 1.19 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, decyl), 1.27 (8H, bs, decyl), 1.39 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, decyl), 1.55–1.63 (2H, m, decyl), 3.09 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 and

7 Hz, decyl), 3.39 (1H, t, *J* 7 and 6.5 Hz, decyl), 3.47 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, decyl), 3.58 (1H, bs, NH), 6.59 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.68 (1H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.16 (2H, t, *J* 8 and 7.5 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 234.3 (M⁺).

9 : (4-Methoxy-phenyl)-methylamine : yield 89%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3434 (N-H), 2923 (-CH₃), 1462 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.81 (3H, s, methyl), 3.75 (3H, s, methoxy), 6.61 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, Ar-H), 6.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 138.2 (M⁺).

10 : Butyl-(4-methoxy-phenyl)amine : yield 90%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3393 (N-H), 2930 (-CH₂-), 1514 (C-C), 1238 (C-O-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.95 (3H, t, *J* 7.35 Hz, butyl), 1.38-1.46 (2H, m, butyl), 1.56-1.61 (2H, m, butyl), 3.06 (2H, t, *J* 7.05 and 7.1 Hz, butyl), 3.30 (1H, bs, NH), 3.74 (3H, s, methoxy), 6.57 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 180.2 (M⁺).

11 : (4-Methoxy-phenyl)-octylamine : yield 88%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3309 (N-H), 2925 (-CH₂-), 1508 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.98 (3H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz, octyl), 1.28-1.39 (10H, m, octyl), 1.59 (2H, q, *J* 9.5 and 7.5 Hz, octyl), 3.06 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, octyl), 3.74 (3H, s, methoxy), 6.58 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 236.3 (M⁺).

12 : Decyl-(4-methoxy-phenyl)amine : yield 87%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3397 (N-H), 2925 (-CH₂-), 1513 (C-C), 1236 (C-O-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.5 and 7 Hz, decyl), 1.27 (12H, bs, decyl), 1.37 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, decyl), 1.57-1.62 (2H, m, decyl), 3.05 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, decyl), 3.74 (3H, s, methoxy), 6.58 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 164.2 (M⁺).

13 : (4-Chloro-phenyl)-methylamine : yield 89%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3134 (N-H), 1397 (-CH₃), 1503 (C-C), 815 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.81 (3H, s, methyl), 3.70 (1H, bs, NH), 6.52 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 141.8 (M⁺).

14 : Butyl-(4-chloro-phenyl)amine : yield 90%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3140 (N-H), 2957 (-CH₂-), 1500 (C-C), 816 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.95 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 and 7 Hz, butyl), 1.38-1.46 (2H, m, butyl), 1.56-1.62 (2H, m, butyl), 3.07 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, butyl), 3.60 (1H, bs, NH), 6.51 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.10 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 183.9 (M⁺).

15 : Allylphenethylamine : yield 85%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3135 (N-H), 2925 (-CH₂-), 1398 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.82 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 6.5 Hz, phenethyl), 2.89

(2H, t, *J* 6.5 and 7 Hz, phenethyl), 3.27 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, allyl), 5.08 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, allyl), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz, allyl), 5.87 (1H, t, *J* 10.5 and 6.5 Hz, allyl), 7.21 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, Ar-H), 7.30 (2H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 161.9 (M⁺).

16 : Allylphenylamine : yield 87%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3408 (N-H), 2921 (-CH₂-), 1602 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.78 (2H, d, *J* 5.3 Hz, allyl), 5.16 (1H, t, *J* 0.75 and 9.6 Hz, allyl), 5.28 (1H, d, *J* 17.1 Hz, allyl), 5.92-5.99 (1H, m, allyl), 6.64 (2H, d, *J* 7.85 Hz, Ar-H), 6.72 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.18 (2H, t, *J* 7.75 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 134.1 (M⁺).

17 : Allyl-(4-methoxy-phenyl)amine : yield 88%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3395 (N-H), 2921 (-CH₂-), 1511 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.74 (5H, d, *J* 8 Hz, methoxy and allyl), 5.16 (1H, d, *J* 10.5 Hz, allyl), 5.28 (1H, d, *J* 17.5 Hz, allyl), 5.94-5.99 (1H, m, allyl), 6.62 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 164.2 (M⁺).

18 : *N*-Allyl-benzene-1,2-diamine : yield 86%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3142 (N-H), 1399 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.78 (2H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, allyl), 5.19 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, allyl), 5.30 (1H, t, *J* 16.5 and 1 Hz, allyl), 5.98-6.06 (1H, m, allyl), 6.71 (3H, q, *J* 7.5, 11 and 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.81 (1H, t, *J* 7 and 7.5 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 149.2 (M⁺).

19 and 20 : *N,N'*-Diallyl-benzene-1,2-diamine : yield 90%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3397 (N-H), 2923 (-CH₂-), 1503 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.58 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, allyl), 3.78 (2H, d, *J* 5 Hz, allyl), 5.11-5.32 (4H, m, allyl), 5.81 (1H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, allyl), 6.0-6.06 (1H, m, allyl), 6.72 (2H, t, *J* 11.5 and 4.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.81 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.96 (1H, t, *J* 20 and 8 Hz, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 189.2 (M⁺).

21 : 1,2,5,6-Tetrahydro-benzo(*b*)-[1,4]-diazocine : yield 90%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3430 (N-H), 3018 (-CH₂-), 1215 (C-C), 756 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.92 (2H, bs, NH), 4.01 (4H, s, diazocine), 5.91 (2H, s, diazocine), 6.74 (2H, t, *J* 6 and 7.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.90 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 and 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.10 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ_c 58.30, 116.0, 118.90, 120.72, 124.16, 127.23, 137.82, 142.27; MS : *m/z* 161.3 (M⁺).

22 : 2-Butylaminomethyl-phenylamine : yield 82%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3138 (N-H), 2925 (-CH₂-), 1398 (C-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.92 (3H, s, butyl), 1.18-1.28 (2H, m, butyl), 1.31-1.45 (2H, m, butyl), 2.55 (2H, t, *J* 11.5 Hz, butyl), 3.71 (2H, s, benzyl), 6.52-6.61 (2H, m, Ar-

H), 6.93–7.02 (2H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 13.95, 20.45, 23.19, 49.09, 53.16, 115.77, 124.40, 128.47, 129.68, 146.92; MS : m/z 177.1 (M^+).

23 : 2-Allylaminomethyl-phenylamine : yield 81%; IR (KBr , cm^{-1}) 3149 (N-H), 1616 ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 1400 (C-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.19 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, allyl), 3.73 (2H, s, benzyl), 5.02–5.15 (2H, m, allyl), 5.78–5.89 (1H, m, allyl), 6.60 (2H, t, J 12.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.94–7.04 (2H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 51.63, 52.22, 115.83, 117.72, 123.94, 128.35, 129.90, 136.62, 146.86; MS : m/z 163.0 (M^+).

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